

**Chinese history,
heritage and community
in Tasmania:
A bibliography**

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INTRODUCTION

Over the past three decades, scholarship on the history and heritage of Chinese migrants and their descendants in Australia and New Zealand has flourished, with contributions from academic historians, curators, archaeologists, heritage professionals, and local, family and community researchers. Other than South Australia, Tasmania had the smallest Chinese population of the Australasian colonies over the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries (Table 1), and this is reflected in the comparatively small amount of research undertaken to date on Chinese migration and settlement in Tasmania, particularly beyond the tin-mining communities of the North-East. Most studies in Chinese Australasian history and heritage focus on Victoria and New South Wales, as well as Queensland, the Northern Territory and New Zealand.

Table 1. Chinese population of Tasmania, 1881–1947

	1881	1891	1901	1911	1921	1933	1947
Persons	844	1056	609	529	321	197	111
Male	842	993	536	450	283	160	81
Female	2	63	73	79	38	37	30

Source: *Official Year Book of the Commonwealth of Australia, No. 18, 1925*, Commonwealth Bureau of Census and Statistics, Melbourne, 1925, p. 955; Census of the Commonwealth of Australia, 1933 and 1947.

As this bibliography shows, however, there is a diverse body of research that provides a foundation on which future work on Chinese history and heritage in Tasmania can build – including Helen Vivian’s well-known 1984 study of Chinese heritage sites in the North-East and Adrienne Petty’s 2009 PhD thesis on case studies of early Chinese migrants. Future studies can also look to existing scholarship on Chinese communities in other parts of Australia and New Zealand, and their transnational connections, as a model.

Chinese in Tasmania were part of broader (particularly Cantonese) circulations around the Pacific over the nineteenth and twentieth centuries, and their lives were shaped by the same shifting laws, policies and attitudes – from colonial anti-Chinese laws, to the White Australia Policy, to the Colombo Plan, to multiculturalism. Tasmania as a case study also has much to offer the broader field of overseas Chinese history and heritage, in Australia and New Zealand and beyond, due to its own distinct history as an island colony/state with a small and localized Chinese population, dating from the earliest days of British colonisation to the post-Tiananmen era.

Today Tasmania’s ethnic Chinese population is larger than it has ever been. More than 7,000 Tasmanian residents identify as having Chinese ancestry, and those born overseas have come from mainland China, Hong Kong, Taiwan, Singapore, Macau and beyond (Census 2016). In thinking about Tasmania’s Chinese history, it is also worth thinking about these contemporary Chinese Tasmanian communities and how

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museums, libraries and archives might ensure that they are documented in their collections. Queen Victoria Museum and Art Gallery's unique Guan Di Temple Collection is an example of the important role collecting institutions can play in preserving and documenting the history and heritage of minority communities for the future.

With all this in mind, this bibliography is intended as a research tool to assist with the study of Tasmania's Chinese communities across the nineteenth and twentieth centuries. It documents existing research relating to Chinese people in Tasmania, focusing on history, heritage and community, and provides a survey of publications and other research outputs. Generally, the bibliography only lists work whose principal subject matter is people of Chinese ancestry in Tasmania, while publications that contain only incidental mentions of Chinese people are not included. However, some relevant general studies of Tasmanian history and Chinese Australian history are also included where they touch on Tasmanian Chinese history in meaningful ways.

Material listed in the bibliography is available in the public domain, and most items can be found in the collections of Libraries Tasmania, University of Tasmania Library, National Library of Australia, Queen Victoria Museum and Art Gallery, and/or online. Links to material available online are provided where possible, and material only available online has been saved into the Internet Archive Wayback Machine (<https://archive.org/web/>).

While the focus is on published material, the bibliography includes a brief discussion of archives and manuscript material held in Tasmanian Archives and the National Archives of Australia. It does not, however, list material held in local museums, historical societies or private collections, nor does it include material culture and archaeological collections held in the Tasmanian Museum and Art Gallery, Queen Victoria Museum and Art Gallery, and regional and local museums, such as the St Helens History Room. There is also a wealth of additional primary source material, such as government reports, parliamentary papers, newspapers, genealogical sources and family collections, that goes beyond the scope of this bibliography.

The bibliography was compiled between January and March 2022 by Dr Kate Bagnall. It was commissioned by Kirstie Ross for the Tasmanian Museum and Art Gallery (TMAG) as part of TMAG's Contemporary Migrant Experiences project, with funding from the National Foundation for Australia-China Relations. We would appreciate being notified of corrections and pleased to hear of additional or updated entries for inclusion in future editions.

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HISTORY

Historical research on Tasmania's Chinese communities can be divided into three (somewhat overlapping) categories: academic histories that focus on Chinese in Tasmania; academic histories that mention Chinese in Tasmania; and community, local and public histories that explore Tasmania's Chinese history in various ways and to different extents.

Academic histories on Chinese in Tasmania

Adrienne Petty's 2009 PhD thesis is the most substantial academic study on the history of Tasmania's Chinese community, and it sits alongside a number of History Honours theses also completed at the University of Tasmania, most of which are now quite dated due to advances in scholarship and the increasing availability of relevant sources. A small number of scholarly articles and essays also exist – those by Mobo Gao and Cassandra Pybus emerged from the same ARC Linkage project as Petty's PhD. Of note is Richard Ely's 2001 essay on Andrew Inglis Clark's 1888 Memorandum on Chinese Immigration.

Alcock, Jacquelyn. "The Middle People": A History of the Launceston Chinese Community'. BA Hons thesis, University of Tasmania, 1998.

<https://eprints.utas.edu.au/17769/1/whole-Alcock-thesis.pdf>.

Black, Gordon J. 'T.J.K. Bakhap (1866–1923), A Chinese-Australian?: The Significance of His Public and Political Life in Relation to Prevailing Australian Attitudes to China, the Chinese, and Australia's Place in the World'. BA Hons thesis, University of Tasmania, 1992.

Chung Sing, Willie. 'Personal Account of Jūng Sihng Lóhng – Written for the Authorities during the Land Reform'. Translated by Ely Finch, 2017.

<https://helenechung.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/10/willi-chung-sing-17-08-27.pdf>.

Easteal, B.V. 'The Chinese in Tasmania, 1870–1909'. BA Hons thesis, University of Tasmania, 1966.

Ely, Richard. 'Inglis Clark's 1888 "Memorandum" on Chinese Immigration'. In *A Living Force: Andrew Inglis Clark and the Ideal of Commonwealth*, edited by Richard Ely. Tasmania, Australia: Centre for Tasmanian Historical Studies, University of Tasmania, 2001. <https://eprints.utas.edu.au/11912/>.

Gao, Mobo. 'Early Chinese Migrants to Australia: A Critique of the Sojourner Narrative on Nineteenth-Century Chinese Migration to British Colonies'. *Asian Studies Review* 41, no. 3 (July 2017): 389–404.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/10357823.2017.1336747>.

- Gao, Mobo. *Sojourners or Settlers? Early Chinese Migrants to Australia: A Case Study of Tasmania*. Western Sydney University Institute for Australian and Chinese Arts and Culture Chinese Australian History Online Seminar Series 2. Sydney, New South Wales, 2021.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=irUH3ic3UKM>.
- Paterson, Jai. 'Chinese Community'. In *Companion to Tasmanian History*. Hobart, Tasmania: Centre for Tasmanian Historical Studies, University of Tasmania, 2006.
https://www.utas.edu.au/library/companion_to_tasmanian_history/C/Chinese.htm.
Scattered references to Chinese people can also be found in the Companion to Tasmanian History entries on 'Abalone', 'Buddhism', 'Fishing', 'Ghost Stories', 'Healing', 'Vegetables Other than Potatoes'.
- Petty, Adrienne. 'Deconstructing the Chinese Sojourner: Case Studies of Early Chinese Migrants to Tasmania'. PhD thesis, University of Tasmania, 2009.
<https://eprints.utas.edu.au/15873/>.
- Pybus, Cassandra. 'China in the Tasmanian Imaginary'. *Griffith Review*, January 2013. <https://www.griffithreview.com/articles/china-in-the-tasmanian-imaginary/>.
- Rolls, Eric. 'Flowers and the Wide Sea: China and Australia, with Special Reference to Tasmania'. *Tasmanian Historical Research Association Papers and Proceedings* 36, no. 4 (1989): 131–40.
- Ross, Kaz. 'Imagined Futures and Forgotten Pasts: Tasmania's Asian Connections'. *Journal of Australian Studies* 41, no. 3 (2017): 296–311.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14443058.2017.1347102>.
- Sidebottom, Peter. 'Racism of the Righteous: Tasmanian Attitudes to the Chinese Question in Australia, 1880–1890'. BA Hons thesis, University of Tasmania, 1974.
- Walden, Sue. 'The Tinfields of North East Tasmania – a Regional Variation?' In *Histories of the Chinese in Australasia and the South Pacific*, edited by Paul Macgregor, 177–90. Melbourne, Victoria: Museum of Chinese Australian History, 1995.
- Wu, Qianlong, and Mobo Gao. 'Decoding Historical Scripts in Chinese: The Tasmanian Chungs from Xinhui'. *Journal of Chinese Australia* 2 (October 2006).
<https://webarchive.nla.gov.au/awa/20070702233238/http://pandora.nla.gov.au/pan/50815/20070628-0000/131.172.16.7/jca/issue02/14WuGao.html>.

Other academic histories

Discussion of Tasmania is only seldom found in general histories of Chinese in Australia, and Eric Rolls' epic two-volume study is one of the few where Tasmania receives more than a passing mention.

The histories listed below, however, refer to Chinese in Tasmania in some substantive way, even if it is only small. The list does not include publications where Tasmania is only mentioned in passing (e.g. where Tasmania is named in a list of colonies that had anti-Chinese legislation).

- Bowen, Alister. *Archaeology of the Chinese Fishing Industry in Colonial Victoria*. Sydney: Sydney University Press, 2012.
<https://dx.doi.org/10.30722/sup.9781920899813>.
- . 'The Central Role of Chinese People in Australia's Colonial Fishing Industry'. *Journal of Australian Colonial History* 12 (2010): 97–118.
- Blainey, Geoffrey. *The Peaks of Lyell*. Melbourne: Melbourne University Press, 1954.
- Couchman, Sophie. 'Chinese Australian Brides, Photography, and the White Wedding'. In *Locating Chinese Women: Historical Mobility between China and Australia*, edited by Kate Bagnall and Julia T. Martínez, 45–75. Hong Kong: Hong Kong University Press, 2021.
- Dallas, K.M. 'The Origins of "White Australia"'. *The Australian Quarterly* 27, no. 1 (March 1955): 43–52.
- Finnane, Mark. 'Law as Politics: Chinese Litigants in Australian Colonial Courts'. In *Chinese Australians: Politics, Engagement and Resistance*, edited by Sophie Couchman and Kate Bagnall, 117–36. Leiden: Brill, 2015.
- Fitzgerald, John. 'Revolution and Respectability: Chinese Masons in Australian History'. In *Connected Worlds: History in Transnational Perspective*, edited by Ann Curthoys and Marilyn Lake, 80–110. Canberra: ANU Press, 2005.
<https://press.anu.edu.au/publications/connected-worlds>.
- Hart, Philip R. 'Church of England in Tasmania under Bishop Montgomery, 1889–1901'. Research Master's thesis, University of Tasmania, 2012.
<https://eprints.utas.edu.au/17351/>.
- Hunt, Rodney. 'Social Life on the Tinfields of North East Tasmania, 1874–1930'. BA Hons thesis, University of Tasmania, 1981.
- Jordan, Renée Clare. 'White-Ribboners : The Woman's Christian Temperance Union of Tasmania, 1885-1914'. BA Hons thesis, University of Tasmania, 2001.
<https://eprints.utas.edu.au/17707/>.
- Khoo, Tseen, and Rodney Noonan. 'Wartime Fundraising by Chinese Australian Communities'. *Australian Historical Studies* 42, no. 1 (March 2011): 92–110.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1031461X.2010.541472>.
- Lee, Joseph. 'Anti-Chinese Legislation in Australasia'. *Quarterly Journal of Economics* 3, no. 2 (January 1889): 218–24.
- Price, Charles A. *The Great White Walls Are Built: Restrictive Immigration to North America and Australasia, 1836-1888*. Canberra: Australian Institute of International Affairs in association with Australian National University Press, 1974.
- Robson, Lloyd. *A History of Tasmania. Volume II: Colony and State from 1856 to the 1980s*. Melbourne: Oxford University Press, 1991.
- Rolls, Eric. *Citizens: Flowers and the Wide Sea – Continuing the Epic Story of China's Centuries-Old Relationship with Australia*. St Lucia, Queensland: University of Queensland Press, 1996.

———. *Sojourners: The Epic Story of China's Centuries-Old Relationship with Australia: Flowers and the Wide Sea*. St Lucia, Queensland: University of Queensland Press, 1993.

Community, public and local histories

ABC Education and Jon Addison. *Bound Feet: The Pain of Elegance*. Video recording. Australian Broadcasting Corporation, 2019.

<https://www.abc.net.au/education/bound-feet-the-pain-of-elegance/13624954>.

———. *Chinese Figurines*. Video recording. Australian Broadcasting Corporation, 2019. <https://www.abc.net.au/education/chinese-figurines/13624942>.

———. *Chinese Migration to Tin Mountain*. Video recording. Australian Broadcasting Corporation, 2019. <https://www.abc.net.au/education/chinese-migration-to-tin-mountain/13624922>.

———. *Chinese Temples in 19th-Century Tasmania*. Video recording. Australian Broadcasting Corporation, 2019. <https://www.abc.net.au/education/chinese-temples-in-19th-century-tasmania/13624928>.

Addison, Jon. 'Guan Di and Tin Mountain: Chinese Temples in Northeast Tasmania'. *Newsletter* (International Institute for Asian Studies) 71 (Summer 2015): 56. https://www.iias.asia/sites/default/files/nwl_article/2019-05/IIAS_NL71_56.pdf.

Alexander, Alison. *Glenorchy 1804–1964*. Glenorchy, Tasmania: Glenorchy City Council, 1986.

Beatty, Bill. *Tasmania: Isle of Splendour*. Revised edition. Melbourne: Cassell, 1967.

Beswick, John. *Brothers' Home: The Story of Derby, Tasmania*. Gravelly Beach, Tasmania: R. and D. Beswick, 2003.

Blake, Philip Gerard, and Mary Blake. 'The Chinese in Tasmania'. In *Secret Tasmania*, 123–26. Frenchs Forest, New South Wales: New Holland Publishers (Australia), 2002.

Bolch, Cathie, Jennifer Muggeridge, and Carole Withers. 'The Chinese'. In *Bygone Branxholm, 1883-1983*, 74–77. Branxholm, Tasmania: Branxholm Centenary Committee, 1983.

'Burnie's Chinese Population'. *Tasmanian Ancestry* 14, no. 1 (June 1993): 27.

Chinese Community Association of Tasmania Inc. *50 Year Anniversary Commemorative Magazine*. Hobart, Tasmania: Chinese Community Association of Tasmania Inc., 2019. <https://ccat.asn.au/articles/50-year-anniversary-commemorative-magazine/>.

Chung-Gon, Ai-lin. 'James Chung-Gon: Early Australia China Connection'. *James Chung-Gon: Early Australia China Connections* (website), n.d. <https://webarchive.nla.gov.au/awa/20070902133210/http://www.chung-gon.com/index-standard.htm>.

- Chung Martin, Helene. 'Seeking My Chinese Roots'. *Helene Chung Martin* (blog), 31 July 2017. <https://helenechung.com/uncategorized/seeking-my-chinese-roots-a-tasmanian-taishan-dream/>.
- . 'Village Dream (Tasweekend JULY 22-23, 2017)'. *Helene Chung Martin* (blog), 22 July 2017. <https://helenechung.com/uncategorized/village-dream/>.
- Clark, Linda. 'Chinese Miners at Greenstone Creek and Sir Garnet Creek Chinese Tin Mining Camps'. *Launceston Historical Society Papers and Proceedings* 20 (2008): 26–32.
- Cox, Peter. *Lefroy: Tasmania's Forgotten Gold Town*. George Town, Tasmania: George Town and District Historical Society, 2016.
- . 'The Chinese Gold Miners'. In *Way Back When: People Places and Events...: Contributed Stories about the Early Days of Settlement in Northern Tasmania*, edited by Anne M. Bartlett, 291. Launceston, Tasmania: West Tamar Historical Society in conjunction with the George Town and District Historical Society and the Launceston Historical Society, 2012.
- Dunbabin, Tom. 'Prised Delicacy: Chinese Mutton-Fishers of Tasmania'. *Forty South* 67: 63.
- Dwight, Alan. 'Children of the Dragon'. *Forty South* 37: 38.
- Gardam, Faye. 'Chinese Market Gardeners'. In *Discovering Devonport, Tasmania*, 227–28. East Devonport, Tasmania: Faye Gardam, 2017.
- . *Shifting Sands: A History of the Mersey River, Devonport*. Devonport, Tasmania: Devonport Maritime Museum and Historical Society Inc., 2001.
- . *Sawdust, Sails and Sweat: A History of the River Don Settlement, North-West Coast, Tasmania*. Port Sorell, Tasmania: Faye Gardam, 1996.
- Gee, Lucille. 'Chung Gon Family' (Chapter 14). In *Relbia, Yesterday and Today: 1806–2014*, 76–78. Relbia, Tasmania: Lucille Gee, 2014.
- Gill, Jenny. *Engraved in Memory*. Launceston, Tasmania: Jenny Gill, 1988.
- Goc, Nicola. *Tasmanians Remember*. Sandy Bay, Tasmania: Gentrx Publishing, 1999.
- Haygarth, Nic. 'Mining: A Brief History of the Industry That Shaped Tasmania'. *Forty South* 35: 52.
- Hodgkinson, Dennis. *Characters in Charles Street, Launceston*. Launceston, Tasmania: Dennis Hodgkinson, 1976.
- Hodgkinson, Dennis, and James F. Morrell. *Did You Know? Transcripts from the 7NT Series*. Sydney: Australian Broadcasting Commission, 1980.
- Hughes, Peter. 'The Vision of the Wongs & the Art of China'. *Forty South* 32: 48.
- Janaczewska, Noelle. 'The Mutton-Fishers'. *Eat the Table* (blog), 31 July 2018. <https://eatthetable.com/2018/07/31/the-mutton-fishers/>.

CHINESE HISTORY, HERITAGE AND COMMUNITY IN TASMANIA: A BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Limb, Cathy. 'Our "Celestial" Past: The Excavation of a Nineteenth-Century Mining Site'. *Forty South* 30: 76.
- Loone, A. W. *Tasmania's North-East: A Comprehensive History of North-Eastern Tasmania and Its People*. Launceston, Tasmania: Examiner and Weekly Courier, 1928.
- MacFarlane, W.H. *Macfarlane's History of North East Tasmania*. Edited by John Beswick. Scottsdale, Tasmania: North-Eastern Advertiser, 2007.
- Moore, Susan, and Samantha Meyer. 'Tasmania's Hardy Celestials / What Remains of Tasmania's Celestials?'. *Forty South* 10 (1998): 58–59, 61.
- Morris, John, and Donald Morris. *History in Our Streets: The Origins of Launceston Street Names*. Launceston, Tasmania: Regal Publications, 1989.
- Myrtle Park Committee, ed. *They Told a Tale: From Hilltop to Hollow – a History of Myrtle Park and District*. Launceston, Tasmania: Myrtle Park Committee, 1988.
- Pink, Kerry. *Campsite to City: A History of Burnie 1827–2000*. Burnie, Tasmania: Burnie City Council, 2000.
- Ralph, Rowland B. 'The Chinese Vestry'. *Launceston Historical Society Papers and Proceedings* 8 (1996).
- Reid, Owen W. *The North East*. Hobart, Tasmania: Curriculum Centre, Education Department of Tasmania, 1977.
- Richards, E.R. *The Early Days of St Patrick's River and District*. Launceston, Tasmania: Regal Press, 1987.
- Richardson, Garry. *The Coast: The European History of Scamander, Beaumaris, The Gardens, Ansons Bay, Eddystone Point and Musselroe Bay*. St Helens, Tasmania: Bay of Fires Images and Publishing, 2020.
- . *The Bay: The European History of St Helens*. St Helens, Tasmania: Bay of Fires Images and Publishing, 2019.
- . *Up Country: The History of Goshen, Terryvale, Goulds Country, Priory, the Marshes, Pyengana, West Pyengana, Bullock Drivers and the Sawmills of the Municipality of Portland, North East Tasmania*. St Helens, Tasmania: Bay of Fires Images and Publishing, 2017.
- . *Lottah and the Anchor: The History of a Tin Mine and a Dependent Town: North East Tasmania*. Hobart, Tasmania: Forty South Publishing Pty Ltd, 2016.
- . *Tin Mountain: The European and Chinese History of the Blue Tier, Poimena and Weldborough*. Hobart, Tasmania: Forty South, 2013.
- Rootes, Trevor. 'Miners of the North-East'. *Forty South* 37: 42.
- Smith, Mark. 'Gon but Not Forgotten'. *Forty South* 37: 22.
- Smith, T.H. 'The Chinese'. In *The North East Centenary, 1874–1974*. Launceston, Tasmania: Ansatel, 1974.

CHINESE HISTORY, HERITAGE AND COMMUNITY IN TASMANIA: A BIBLIOGRAPHY

- St Helens District High School, ed. *Then and Now: 100 Years of Schooling in St Helens, 1874–1974, Featuring the Children of Portland*. St Helens, Tasmania: St Helens School, 1974.
- Walden, Sue. 'Chinese in the North East'. *Launceston Historical Society Papers and Proceedings* 3 (1991): 67–79.
- Walden, Sue, and Geoff Wilson. 'Chinese' (Chapter 17). In *As the River Flows: Mount Victoria to Boobyalla – a History of Ringarooma Municipality*, edited by Dorothy Beswick. Ringarooma, Tasmania: Ringarooma Council with the aid of the Australian Bicentennial Authority, 1988.
- Whiteley, Monissa. 'Cemeteries & Graves: Chinese (Blog Category Archives)'. A *Blog In Search of a Title* (blog). Accessed 16 February 2022.
<https://monissa.com/why/category/locations/cemeteries-graves/chinese-graves/>.
- . 'Chinese Temples of Tasmania (Blog Category Archives)'. A *Blog In Search of a Title* (blog). Accessed 16 February 2022.
<https://monissa.com/why/category/native-place/china-native-place/chinese-temples-of-tasmania/>.
- Williams, Michael. 'Tasmania: A Short (Chinese) History'. *Newsletter* (Chinese Australian Historical Society), June 2020. <http://nla.gov.au/nla.obj-2769277841>.
- Wooley, Charles. 'Chinatown: It Would Wok around the Clock ...' *Tasmanian Times* (blog), 26 April 2015. <https://tasmaniantimes.com/2015/04/chinatown/>.

BIOGRAPHY

Biographical profiles of individual Chinese Tasmanians and their families can be found in a range of publications, from the *Australian Dictionary of Biography* and the *Companion to Tasmanian History* to public history websites and personal blogs. Generally, these biographies focus on a small number of historical and public figures, including merchant James Chung Gon and family, merchant Chin Kaw, senator Thomas Bakhap, and journalist Helene Chung Martin and family.

Digitisation and indexing of archival material, particularly material available through the Tasmanian Names Index and Trove, means that it is now much easier to locate historical and genealogical information about individual Chinese Tasmanians. A number of works below, such as Monissa Whiteley's blog, suggest the scope of material that can now be located and compiled.

The publications listed below focus on individual Chinese Tasmanians and families. Scattered references to other individuals can be found in general publications on Tasmanian history.

The Tasmanian Family History Society's Comprehensive Subject Index (CSI) is a useful source to locate further references to individual Chinese. The CSI is a searchable database of references to named people, objects, places or events in publications held by the TFHS branch libraries. It can be accessed on the TFHS Inc. website at <https://www.tasfhs.org/csi.php>.

Alexander, Alison. 'Chung Family'. In *Companion to Tasmanian History*. Hobart, Tasmania: Centre for Tasmanian Historical Studies, University of Tasmania, 2006. https://www.utas.edu.au/library/companion_to_tasmanian_history/C/Chung%20family.htm.

Anderson, Kari. 'A Chinese Heritage'. *Pioneers of the Tasmanian Northwest* (blog), 5 June 2018. <http://www.tasmanianpioneers.com/1/post/2018/06/a-chinese-heritage.html>.

Bagnall, Kate. 'The Hung Family of Lefroy, Tasmania'. *The Tiger's Mouth* (blog), 16 October 2020. <https://chineseaustralia.org/the-hung-family-of-lefroy-tasmania/>.

Black, Gordon J. 'T.J.K. Bakhap (1866–1923), A Chinese-Australian?: The Significance of His Public and Political Life in Relation to Prevailing Australian Attitudes to China, the Chinese, and Australia's Place in the World'. BA Hons thesis, University of Tasmania, 1992.

Cassidy, Jill. 'Chung Gon, James (1854–1952)'. In *Australian Dictionary of Biography*. Canberra: National Centre of Biography, Australian National University, 1993. <https://adb.anu.edu.au/biography/chung-gon-james-9745>.

Chinese-Australian Historical Images in Australia project. 'Chinn, Frank (Tung Foo) – Biographical Entry'. *Chinese-Australian Historical Images in Australia* (online database), 2011. <https://www.chia.chinesemuseum.com.au/biogs/CH00062b.htm>.

- . 'Kay, Henry – Biographical Entry'. *Chinese-Australian Historical Images in Australia* (online database), 2011.
<https://www.chia.chinesemuseum.com.au/biogs/CH00538b.htm>.
- . 'Moy, Charles – Biographical Entry'. *Chinese-Australian Historical Images in Australia* (online database), 2009.
<https://www.chia.chinesemuseum.com.au/biogs/CH01844b.htm>.
- . 'Tueon, George Thomas – Biographical Entry'. *Chinese-Australian Historical Images in Australia* (online database), 2008.
<https://www.chia.chinesemuseum.com.au/biogs/CH01322b.htm>.
- . 'Wah Sin – Biographical Entry'. *Chinese-Australian Historical Images in Australia* (online database), 2013.
<https://www.chia.chinesemuseum.com.au/biogs/CH01888b.htm>.
- . 'Wong Hee, Charles – Biographical'. *Chinese-Australian Historical Images in Australia* (online database), 2005.
<https://www.chia.chinesemuseum.com.au/biogs/CH00695b.htm>.
- Chinese Community Association of Tasmania Inc. *50 Year Anniversary Commemorative Magazine*. Hobart, Tasmania: Chinese Community Association of Tasmania Inc., 2019. <https://ccat.asn.au/articles/50-year-anniversary-commemorative-magazine/>.
- 'Chin Kaw'. In *Wikipedia*, 3 February 2022.
https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Chin_Kaw&oldid=1069636500.
- Chung-Gon, Ai-lin. 'James Chung-Gon: Early Australia China Connection'. *James Chung-Gon: Early Australia China Connections* (website), n.d.
<https://webarchive.nla.gov.au/awa/20070902133210/http://www.chung-gon.com/index-standard.htm>.
- Chung Gon, Edward. 'James Chung Gon (Part One) : Immigration Place'. *Immigration Place Australia* (website), n.d.
<https://immigrationplace.com.au/story/james-chung-gon-part-one/>.
- . 'James Chung Gon (Part Two) : Immigration Place'. *Immigration Place Australia* (website), n.d. <https://immigrationplace.com.au/story/james-chung-gon-part-two/>.
- Chung, Helene. 'Helene Chung Martin'. In *Significant Tasmanian Women*. Tasmania, Australia: Department of Communities Tasmania, n.d.
https://www.communities.tas.gov.au/csr/information_and_resources/significant_tasmanian_women/significant_tasmanian_women_-_research_listing/helene_chung_martin.
- . *A Chinese Tasmanian Heritage: Women Past, Present and Future*. Public lecture. Hobart, Tasmania: University of Tasmania, 2015.
<https://livestream.com/universityoftasmania/events/3812330>.

- Chung Martin, Helene. 'Death of Tasmania's Chinese Elder' [Charles Pak Koon Chung]. *Helene Chung Martin* (blog), 9 January 2019. <https://helenechung.com/uncategorized/death-of-tasmanias-chinese-elder/>.
- . 'Dynasty Head Dies at 98' [Charles Pak Koon Chung]. *Helene Chung Martin* (blog), 9 January 2019. <https://helenechung.com/uncategorized/dynasty-head-dies-at-98/>.
- . 'Tasmanian Tin Miners, Addicts and Merchants'. *Chinese Heritage of Australian Federation* (website), 27 February 2009. <https://arrow.latrobe.edu.au/store/3/4/5/5/1/public/stories/henry.htm>.
- . *Ching Chong China Girl: From Fruitshop to Foreign Correspondent*. Sydney: ABC Books, 2008.
- . 'Helene Chung's Family Background: Tasmanian Tin Miners, Addicts and Merchants'. *Helene Chung Martin* (blog), 1 July 2000. <https://helenechung.com/uncategorized/helene-chungs-family-background-tasmanian-tin-miners-addicts-and-merchants-july-2000/>.
- . *Shouting from China*. Ringwood, Victoria: Penguin, 1988.
- Collins, Carolyn, and Roy Eccleston. 'Gladys Sym Choon' [Gladys Chung Gon]. In *Trailblazers: 100 Inspiring South Australian Women*, 262–64. Mile End, South Australia: Wakefield Press, 2019.
- Haygarth, Nic. 'Henry Thom Sing, Chinese Entrepreneur, and the Arthur River Gold Rush 1872'. *Nic Haygarth: Author* (blog), 9 December 2016. <https://nichaygarth.com/index.php/2016/12/09/henry-thom-sing-chinese-entrepreneur-and-the-arthur-river-gold-rush-1872/>.
- Hunt, Janine. 'William Owen (Ow-En): My Chinese Ancestor'. *Tasmanian Ancestry* (December 2012): 133–34.
- Leong, Greg. 'Greg Leong'. *The Partnership Project* (website), n.d. <https://www.thepartnershipproject.net.au/gregleong-story>.
- Liew, K.S. 'Chin Kaw (1865–1922)'. In *Australian Dictionary of Biography*. Canberra: National Centre of Biography, Australian National University, 1979. <https://adb.anu.edu.au/biography/chin-kaw-5581>.
- Manning, Catherine. 'Gladys Sym Choon' [Gladys Chung Gon]. *Adelaidia* (website), 6 December 2013. <https://adelaidia.history.sa.gov.au/people/gladys-sym-choon>.
- Museum of Chinese Australian History. 'Lula Chinn'. *Culture Victoria: Chinese Australian Families* (website), n.d. <https://cv.vic.gov.au/stories/immigrants-and-emigrants/chinese-australian-families/lula-chinn/>.
- . 'The Wedding of Gladys Sym Choon and Edward Chung Gon, in Adelaide, 1939'. *Culture Victoria: Chinese Australian Families* (website), n.d. <https://cv.vic.gov.au/stories/immigrants-and-emigrants/chinese-australian-families/the-wedding-of-gladys-sym-choon-and-edward-chung-gon-in-adelaide-1939/>.

CHINESE HISTORY, HERITAGE AND COMMUNITY IN TASMANIA: A BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Petty, Adrienne. 'Ah Moy'. In *Companion to Tasmanian History*. Hobart, Tasmania: Centre for Tasmanian Historical Studies, University of Tasmania, 2006.
https://www.utas.edu.au/library/companion_to_tasmanian_history/M/Moy%20Ah.htm.
- . 'Chin Kaw'. In *Companion to Tasmanian History*. Hobart, Tasmania: Centre for Tasmanian Historical Studies, University of Tasmania, 2006.
https://www.utas.edu.au/library/companion_to_tasmanian_history/K/Chin%20Kaw.htm.
- Petty Gao, Adrienne. 'Thomas Jerome Kingston Bakhap'. *ABC Radio National* (website), 11 October 2005.
<https://www.abc.net.au/radionational/programs/archived/perspective/adrienne-petty--gao/3361610>.
- Quirk, Marilyn. *Tasmania, an Island Far Away: Migrant Stories*. Launceston, Tasmania: Regal Publications, 2010.
- Rubinstein, Hilary L. 'Bakhap, Thomas Jerome Kingston (1866–1923) – Senator for Tasmania, 1913–23 (Liberal Party; Nationalist Party)'. In *Biographical Dictionary of the Australian Senate*. Canberra, Australia: Parliament of Australia, 2000.
<https://biography.senate.gov.au/thomas-jerome-kingston-bakhap/>.
- The Tasmanian Cyclopaedia: An Historical, Industrial and Commercial Review: Biographical Facts Showing the Progress of Tasmania* [Edward Chung Gon and Chin Kaw]. Hobart, Tasmania: Service Publishing Co., 1931.
- Walker, Tim. 'The Chung-Gon Family in Northern Tasmania'. *ABC Local* (website), 8 February 2013. <https://www.abc.net.au/local/stories/2013/02/08/3686482.htm>.
- Whiteley, Monissa. 'Chinese to Tasmania (Blog Category Archives)'. *A Blog In Search of a Title* (blog), 2019. <https://monissa.com/why/category/native-place/china-native-place/chinese-tasmania/>.

HERITAGE, ARCHAEOLOGY AND TOURISM

Chinese heritage studies in Tasmania have focused on the former tin-mining areas of the north-east of the state. Most significant is Helen Vivian's 1985 study, 'Tasmania's Chinese Heritage', which provides information about 41 identified sites in the North-East including Chinese camps, joss houses, market gardens and cemeteries. Interpretation at some of these sites features stories of the Chinese people who lived and worked there. While no joss house buildings remain in situ, temple materials from these sites make up the Guan Di Temple Collection in the Queen Victoria Museum and Art Gallery in Launceston.

The Trail of the Tin Dragon project, an ambitious and now-defunct heritage tourism initiative, was established in the early 2000s and sought to boost tourism through the establishment of a Chinese heritage trail through Launceston, Scottsdale, Branxholm, Derby, Moorina, Weldborough, Blue Tier and St Helens. The relevant local councils, as well as Forestry Tasmania, were partners on a 2003 ARC Linkage project (LP0347077) by Mobo Gao and Cassandra Pybus from the University of Tasmania. The outcomes of this Linkage project, including Adrienne Petty's PhD thesis, are listed in 'Academic histories' above.

Around the same time (2004–2005), a Tasmanian working group (led by Mobo Gao) of the national Chinese-Australian Cultural Heritage (CACH) project was active; a substantial bibliography, entitled '*The Hidden Dragon*', was produced by this group and is held in the Queen Victoria Museum and Art Gallery Library (see full reference below).

Bell, Peter. 'Archaeology of the Chinese in Australia'. *Australian Historical Archaeology* 14 (1996): 13–18.

Campbell, Bob, and Lynda Jones. 'Master Plan for "The Trail of the Tin Dragon": A Themed Trail for North-East Tasmania'. Launceston, Tasmania: Groupwork for Dorset EDG, May 2004. [https://stors.tas.gov.au/au-7-0095-00088\\$stream](https://stors.tas.gov.au/au-7-0095-00088$stream).

Davis, Robyn, Anne Lucadou-Welld, Jai Paterson, Peta Newman, John Snedden, and Robert Stephens. '*The Hidden Dragon: Revealing the Story of the Chinese Contribution to the Tasmanian Community*'. Launceston and Hobart, Tasmania: Queen Victoria Museum and Art Gallery and University of Tasmania, 2005.

Evans, Kathryn. 'The Kent/Chintock Battery and Waterwheel: Conservation Assessment – Part One: Historical Research Project'. Launceston, Tasmania: Forestry Commission, 1992.

Forestry Tasmania. *The Tin Dragon* (video recording). DVD. Hobart, Tasmania: Forestry Tasmania, 2005.

Gaughwin, Denise. 'Chinese Settlement Sites in North East Tasmania: An Archaeological View'. In *Histories of the Chinese in Australasia and the South Pacific*, edited by Paul Macgregor, 230–48. Melbourne, Victoria: Museum of Chinese Australian History, 1995.

CHINESE HISTORY, HERITAGE AND COMMUNITY IN TASMANIA: A BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Gaughwin, Denise. 'North East Tasmania Historic Sites Inventory Project'. Launceston, Tasmania: Forestry Commission, 1991.
- Jennings, Jeff. *The Branxholm Joss House* (video recording). Dorset, Tasmania: Dorset Tasmania History Society, 2021. <https://fb.watch/b5H3Rr282W/>.
- . *The Branxholm Joss House: Interview with Doug Beswick* (video recording). Dorset, Tasmania: Dorset Tasmania History Society, 2021. <https://fb.watch/b5H0rtdw9h/>.
- Paterson, Jai. 'Chinese Memorial: Moorina Cemetery'. Launceston, Tasmania: Dorset Council, n.d. Held by Queen Victoria Museum and Art Gallery.
- Kok, Hu Jin and Queen Victoria Museum and Art Gallery. 'Catalogue and Conservation Report for Queen Victoria Museum and Art Gallery ... : Collection of Remnants of Nineteenth Century Chinese Joss Houses from North East Tasmania (Gold and Tin Mining Districts)'. Launceston, Tasmania: Queen Victoria Museum and Art Gallery, 2005.
- Sentience Group. 'The Trail of the Tin Dragon: Business Development Plan – Part B'. Launceston, Tasmania: The Sentience Group, August 2005. <https://nla.gov.au/nla.obj-1382115997>.
- Sentience Group, Bob Campbell, and Brian Green. 'The Trail of the Tin Dragon: Market Assessment and Viability Business Development Plan – Part A'. Launceston, Tasmania: The Sentience Group, April 2005. <https://nla.gov.au/nla.obj-1382116361>.
- Tasmanian Family History Society, ed. *TAMIOT: Tombstone and Memorial Inscriptions of Tasmania*. Electronic resource. 2nd ed. Launceston, Tasmania: Tasmanian Family History Society Inc., 2010.
- Trail of the Tin Dragon. *Trail of the Tin Dragon* (website), n.d. <https://webarchive.nla.gov.au/awa/20150228001531/http://www.trailofthetindragon.com.au/>.
- Trail of the Tin Dragon. *The Trail of Tin Dragon* (video recording), 2012. <https://youtu.be/tUMXJ-4ErqQ>.
- Trail of the Tin Dragon Steering Committee. 'The Trail of the Tin Dragon Project Update'. Trail of the Tin Dragon Steering Committee, 2005. <https://nla.gov.au/nla.obj-1837913262>.
- Vivian, Helen. 'Tasmania's Chinese Heritage: An Historical Record of Chinese Sites in North East Tasmania'. Launceston, Tasmania: Australian Heritage Commission and the Queen Victoria Museum and Art Gallery, 1985. <https://eprints.utas.edu.au/17370/>.

ORAL HISTORY

A number of Chinese Tasmanians have been interviewed for oral history projects, including those undertaken by Diana Giese and Paul Macgregor in conjunction with the National Library of Australia. These are listed below along with oral histories held by Queen Victoria Museum and Art Gallery and other relevant recorded interviews and transcripts.

The collection of further oral histories, particularly with older members of the contemporary Chinese Tasmanian community, is of critical importance and would enable the telling of a more complete story of Tasmania's Chinese past, including its twentieth-century history and the lives of Chinese Tasmanian women.

Cassidy, Jill, and Elspeth Wishart, eds. *Launceston Talks: Oral Histories of the Launceston Community*. Launceston, Tasmania: Regal Publications for the Queen Victoria Museum and Art Gallery, 1990.

Chin, Mey Chee Fui, and Ian Terry. Mey Chee Fui Chin interviewed by Ian Terry for the 'Everyone is Human: Stories of Recent Migration' project, Tasmanian Museum and Art Gallery. Video recording and transcript, 2014. Tasmanian Museum and Gallery.

https://www.tmag.tas.gov.au/whats_on/exhibitions/current_upcoming/exhibitions/everyone_is_human_stories_of_recent_migration.

Chinn, Frank, and Constant Wong. Frank Chinn interviewed by Constant Wong. Sound recording and transcript, c. 1980s. Museum of Chinese Australian History, Melbourne.

Chinn, Frank, and Morag Loh. Interviews with Mr Frank Chinn, 1980. Oral History Interviews with Chinese Immigrants and their Descendants, MS 14434. Sound recording (6 cassette tapes), 1980. State Library of Victoria.

<http://handle.slv.vic.gov.au/10381/160982>.

Chung-Gon, Bob, and Tim Walker. The Chung-Gon family heritage. Sound recording, 2013.

https://abcmedia.akamaized.net/local/northtas/201302/r1070410_12626365.mp3.

Part of Walker, Tim. 'The Chung-Gon Family in Northern Tasmania'. ABC Local (website), 8 February 2013.

<https://www.abc.net.au/local/stories/2013/02/08/3686482.htm>.

———. The story of James Chung-Gon. Sound recording, 2013.

https://abcmedia.akamaized.net/local/northtas/201302/r1070403_12626293.mp3.

Part of Walker, Tim. 'The Chung-Gon Family in Northern Tasmania'. ABC Local (website), 8 February 2013.

<https://www.abc.net.au/local/stories/2013/02/08/3686482.htm>.

CHINESE HISTORY, HERITAGE AND COMMUNITY IN TASMANIA: A BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Moy, William (Bill), and Janice Moy. Janice Moy interviewing her father William (Bill) Moy, 29 January 1984. Transcript. *James Chung-Gon: Early Australia China Connections* (website), n.d.
https://web.archive.org/web/20220220031138/http://www.chung-gon.com/brief_bill-moy_1.htm.
- Chung Martin, Helene, and Diana Giese. Helene Chung Martin, journalist and author, interviewed by Diana Giese in the Chinese Australian Oral History Partnership collection. Sound recording, 2000. National Library of Australia.
<https://nla.gov.au/nla.cat-vn1907700>.
- Chung Martin, Helene, and Ian Terry. Helene Chung Martin, journalist and author, interviewed by Ian Terry to accompany her donation to the Tasmanian Museum and Art Gallery. Sound recording and transcript, 2017. Tasmanian Museum and Art Gallery.
- Cremin, Thelma, and Paul Macgregor. Thelma Cremin interviewed by Paul Macgregor for the Australia-China Oral History Project. Sound recording, 1994. National Library of Australia. <https://nla.gov.au/nla.obj-206148589>.
- Gooley, Jean Tai-Linn, and Elizabeth Saunders. Jean Tai-Linn Gooley interviewed by Elizabeth Saunders for the Australia-China Oral History Project. Sound recording, 1994. National Library of Australia. <https://nla.gov.au/nla.obj-206148589>.
- Henry, Monica, and Diana Giese. Monica Henry, Chinese Australian, interviewed by Diana Giese in the Chinese Australian Oral History Partnership collection. Sound recording, 2000. National Library of Australia. <https://nla.gov.au/nla.cat-vn411650>.
- Lee, Joyce Therese, and Diana Giese. Joyce Lee interviewed by Diana Giese in the Chinese Australian Oral History Partnership collection. Sound recording, 2000. National Library of Australia. <https://nla.gov.au/nla.cat-vn412070>.
- Lim, Hong, and Diana Giese. Hong Lim interviewed by Diana Giese for the Post-war Chinese Australians Oral History Project. Sound recording, 1996. National Library of Australia. <https://nla.gov.au/nla.cat-vn1194573>.
- Queen Victoria Museum and Art Gallery Oral History Collection:
- QVM:1988:BOHP:0010. Irving Fong. Chinese in Launceston: market gardener, grocer. No publication without permission.
- QVM:1988:BOHP:0011. Lew Sing. Chinese in Launceston: market gardener.
- QVM:1988:BOHP:12. David Ku. Chinese in Launceston: dentist. No publication without staff permission.
- QVM:1988:BOHP:0013A & B. Tiam Lim. Chinese in Launceston: engineer. Only transcript available. No publication without permission.
- QVM:1991:OH:0002 A-C. Doris Chung Gon. Chinese in Launceston: Chung Gon family. Only transcript available.
- QVM:1991:OH:0002 A-C. Ann Fong. Chinese in Launceston: Chung Gon family. Only transcript available.

CHINESE HISTORY, HERITAGE AND COMMUNITY IN TASMANIA: A BIBLIOGRAPHY

QVM:1996:OH:0297 A-B. Phil Bell. Chinese in North-East: Garibaldi, Ah Moy, Ruby Flat.

QVM:1996:OH:0297 A-B. Tas Kincade. Chinese in North-East: Garibaldi, Ah Moy, Ruby Flat.

QVM:1996:OH:0298 A-C. Brian Shean. Chinese in North-East: fieldwork at Garibaldi. Recorded 1993.

QVM:1996:OH:0299. Rod Smith. Chinese in North-East: Cascades, Ah Sheen's store.

QVM:1996:OH:0300. Bill Butt. Chinese in North-East: Weldborough.

QVM:2002:OH:0008 (Radio). Greg Leong. 'Hindsight' on Launceston: 19th-century Chinese, singing quilts, sings 'Waltzing Matilda' in Chinese. QVMAG does not own copyright.

Sym Choon, Gladys, and Patricia Sumerling. Interview with Gladys Sym Choon [Gladys Chung Gon]. Sound recording, 1990. J.D. Somerville Oral History Collection, State Library of South Australia.

<https://catalog.slsa.sa.gov.au:443/record=b2177063~S1>.

Vivian, Helen. 'Appendix 3: Oral History Transcripts' [including interviews with Frank Chinn, Brian Shean and William Moy]. In 'Tasmania's Chinese Heritage: An Historical Record of Chinese Sites in North East Tasmania'. Launceston, Tasmania: Australian Heritage Commission and the Queen Victoria Museum and Art Gallery, 1985. <https://eprints.utas.edu.au/17370/>.

PHOTOGRAPHS

Tasmania's libraries, museums and historical societies hold a range of photographs relating to the local Chinese community and Chinese heritage. As an example, a small number of individual items are detailed below, but not all photographs are listed on public databases or in finding aids. In particular, Queen Victoria Museum and Art Gallery's Kaw Collection contains a significant collection of studio portraits and family photographs that are, as yet, uncatalogued.

As demonstrated by the Kaw Collection and by the *Chinese-Australian Historical Images in Australia* listing below, personal and family photographic collections (held by both Chinese and non-Chinese Tasmanians) are likely to hold further material of relevance and significance. A dedicated project to locate, identify and document relevant Chinese Tasmanian photographs would be beneficial to telling a richer story of the state's history, particularly across the twentieth century.

'Group portrait of the Chung Gon family taken possibly at Lilydale, Tasmania, c 1905. Back row (LtoR): Joseph, Daisy, Rose, Violet, Lily. Middle row (LtoR): Mrs Mary Chung Gon holding baby Edward (Teddy), Esther, Mr James Chung Gon, Albert. Front row (LtoR): Samuel, Ann.' QVM:1995:P:0379. Queen Victoria Museum and Art Gallery.

King, H.J. 'View of three Chinese men standing on or in front of the verandah of the Chinese temple (Joss House), Garibaldi, Tasmania, 1914 (May or earlier).' QVM:1983:P:1618. Queen Victoria Museum and Art Gallery.

Museum of Chinese Australian History. 'Chinese-Australian Historical Images in Australia: Tasmania'. *Chinese-Australian Historical Images in Australia* (online database), 2005. <https://www.chia.chinesemuseum.com.au/biogs/CH00521b.htm>.

'Photograph - Chinese hut in North East Tasmania. Weekly Courier 18/02/1905 p23. Photographer - Abra'. LPIC147/2/181. Tasmanian Archives. <https://stors.tas.gov.au/AI/LPIC147-2-181>.

'Photograph - Chinese tin miner Kit Kap at Bradshaws Creek (original photograph taken in 1914)'. AB713/1/9921. Tasmanian Archives. <https://stors.tas.gov.au/AI/AB713-1-9921>.

'Photograph - View of South Launceston and Chung Gon Chinese market garden. Originally published in the *Examiner* newspaper 4/8/1954'. LPIC147/4/213. Tasmanian Archives. <https://stors.tas.gov.au/LPIC147-4-213>.

COMMUNITY, ART AND IDENTITY

Only a small amount of material created by or about Tasmania's contemporary Chinese communities are held in public collections or are available online, but these include commemorative publications by the Chinese Community Association of Tasmania (est. 1969) and the Wellspring Anglican Church Chinese Congregation (est. 1989). Contemporary creative works reflecting on Tasmanian Chinese history include a historical novel by John Biggs and visual art projects by Greg Leong and Chen Ping.

As with oral histories and photographs, community archiving projects or efforts to encourage individuals and community organisations to donate or deposit material in relevant collecting institutions would support future work in Chinese Tasmanian history and heritage.

Biggs, John B. *Tin Dragons* [historical fiction]. Rosny Park, Tasmania: Maygog Publishing, 2008.

Chen, Ping. *Unseen Mountain*. Hobart, Tasmania: Chen Ping Studio, 2014.

Chinese Community Association of Tasmania Inc. 'Chinese Community Association of Tasmania Inc. 澳洲塔省華人聯誼會'. Organisation website. Chinese Community Association of Tasmania. Accessed 5 February 2022. <https://ccat.asn.au/>.

Chinese Community Association of Tasmania Inc. *50 Year Anniversary Commemorative Magazine*. Hobart, Tasmania, Australia: Chinese Community Association of Tasmania Inc., 2019. <https://ccat.asn.au/articles/50-year-anniversary-commemorative-magazine/>.

Chung, Charles. 'The Old and the New – Chinese Community Association of Tasmania Inc.' Chinese Community Association of Tasmania Inc., 30 May 2016. <https://ccat.asn.au/articles/the-old-and-the-new-by-charles-chung/>.

Church of England in Tasmania. 'The Chinese Mission in Tasmania (under John Yung Choy, Catechist): First Report'. Hobart, Tasmania: Church of England in Tasmania, 1895.

Hope, Anthony, and Jason Zhe Xu. *Showcasing Tasmania and the Connection to Fujian China*. Moonah, Tasmania: Franklin Direct, 2017.

Launceston Chinese Association. 'Newsletter / Launceston Chinese Association Inc.' Launceston, Tasmania, 1996–2000. https://stors.tas.gov.au/ILS/SD_ILS-71815.

Leong, Greg. *Greg Leong's Singing History Quilts for New Chinese Australians: Swagman, Shearer, Bushranger and Chinaman Tin Miner*. Launceston, Tasmania: Greg Leong, 2001.

Mo, Yimei. 'Self-Perception of the Chinese in Tasmania'. PhD thesis, Australian National University, 1994. Embargoed until 2033. <http://hdl.handle.net/1885/11017>.

Wellspring Anglican Church Chinese Congregation. *Wellspring Anglican Church Chinese Congregation 30th Anniversary Magazine (1989–2019)*. Sandy Bay, Tasmania: Wellspring Anglican Church Chinese Congregation, 2019.

———. *Wellspring Anglican Church Chinese Congregation 25th Anniversary Magazine (1989–2014)*. Sandy Bay, Tasmania: Wellspring Anglican Church Chinese Congregation, 2014.

ARCHIVES AND MANUSCRIPTS

There is a wealth of primary source material that can be used to tell the history of Chinese people in Tasmania over the nineteenth and twentieth centuries – including heritage sites, archaeological remains, material culture collections held in museums and private hands, family photographs and heirlooms, intangible cultural heritage practices, and documentary heritage such as historical publications, archives and manuscripts.

What follows is an overview of relevant archival material held by Tasmanian Archives (part of Libraries Tasmania) and the National Archives of Australia. Some of this is available online, as are other useful sources including:

- historical newspapers in Trove (<https://trove.nla.gov.au>)
- Tasmanian Parliamentary Papers 1856–1901 (<https://www.parliament.tas.gov.au/tpl/PPWeb/>)
- genealogical records in Ancestry.com (e.g. Tasmanian Police Gazette) and FamilySearch (e.g. Tasmanian Government Gazette).

Tasmanian Archives / Libraries Tasmania

Tasmanian Archives and Libraries Tasmania hold and provide access to archival and manuscript material relating to Chinese Tasmanians in both the nineteenth and twentieth centuries; Libraries Tasmania also holds copies of many of the publications listed in this bibliography.

Tasmanian government archives of relevance include records relating to: birth, death and marriage; convicts; naturalisation; land and property; shipping; Colonial Secretary's Office; courts and prisoners; bankruptcy; wills. Many records have been indexed, and digitised, and are available through the Tasmanian Names Index: https://libriestas.ent.sirsiidynix.net.au/client/en_AU/names/.

Chung Martin, Helene. 'Helene Chung Martin'. Archives agency. NG2448.
Tasmanian Archives. <https://stors.tas.gov.au/AI/NG2448>.

Hodgkinson, Dennis. 'Dennis Hodgkinson'. Archives agency. NG2678. Tasmanian Archives. <https://stors.tas.gov.au/AI/NG2678>.

'The Hidden Dragon' bibliography lists various items relating to the history of Chinese people in Launceston in the Dennis Hodgkinson collection. Materials held in Launceston.

Thompson, John Frederick. 'File – The Chinese in Tasmania: Newspaper Clippings'. Archives item. 1994–2007. NS6052/1/163. Tasmanian Archives. <https://stors.tas.gov.au/AI/NS6052-1-163>.

National Archives of Australia

The National Archives of Australia holds records relating to Chinese Tasmanians, most of which date from after Federation in 1901. Particularly significant are records relating to immigration, customs, naturalisation and alien registration. These records are held in Hobart and interstate, and access to these records varies.

For example, series A396 (Alien Registration Papers – Chinese, Tasmania) is fully described at item level and all 293 items are digitised, while P437, the main correspondence series of the Customs Department in Tasmania, is only partially described at item level, with an even smaller number of items digitised. P437 covers almost 95 shelf metres but only 4960 items are listed in RecordSearch and 23 are digitised. Further descriptive work on this series would open up significant material relating to Chinese migration and settlement in Tasmania and would be particularly beneficial to descendants seeking to know more about their family's pasts.

The National Archives has published two research guides – one on Chinese records and one on Tasmanian records – that are of use in locating relevant materials.

Jones, Paul. *Chinese-Australian Journeys: Records on Travel, Migration and Settlement, 1860–1975*. National Archives of Australia Research Guides 21. Canberra: National Archives of Australia, 2005. <https://www.naa.gov.au/help-your-research/research-guides/chinese-australian-journeys-records-travel-migration-and-settlement>.

Piggott, Michael. *Commonwealth Government Records about Tasmania: Research Guide*. National Archives of Australia Research Guides 23. Canberra: National Archives of Australia, 2013. <https://www.naa.gov.au/help-your-research/research-guides/commonwealth-government-records-about-tasmania-0>.